

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

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No. 41

• France

Pseudo-nitzschia australis on French Atlantic coast - an unusual toxic bloom

The occurrence of the toxic diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia australis* was first suspected in a water sample from Bay of Brest, France, in 1995 (Fig. 1). At this time, and because of very low number of cells, the identification could not be confirmed by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). In autumn 2004, this species was again reported, and in association with *P. multiseriata*, suspected to be the source of domoic acid (DA) in king scallops (*Pecten maximus*) from the Bay of Seine (English Channel) [1]. Since 2006, it has been encountered every year at low concentrations in either spring or autumn along the Atlantic coast of Brittany.

This year, it was first observed in early March in the Bay of Douarnenez and bloomed a week later in the "Pertuis Charentais" area with densities exceeding 10^6 cells L^{-1} (Fig. 1). It then for more than a month remained noticeable (from 10^5 to 10^6 cells L^{-1}) in several areas of the Atlantic coast

(Fig. 1). At the same time, the monitoring network (REPHY of Ifremer) detected domoic acid far above the EU-regulatory limit of 20 mg DA/Kg tissue in shellfish (up to 10 times the safety threshold), leading to the prohibition of harvesting and sale of scallops during several weeks.

In contrast to other years where toxic blooms were dominated by species of the *Pseudo-nitzschia pseudodelicatissima/cuspidata* complex [2] as defined by Lundholm *et al.* [3], this year was notable for a species of the *Pseudo-nitzschia seriata* complex *sensu* Hasle [4]. An identification key using features observable in Light Microscope (LM) led us to think that it was *Pseudo-nitzschia australis* with asymmetrical lanceolate valves, a width varying from 7.0 to 8.9 μm , apices slightly rostrate and a 23-31% overlap of cells in chains (Fig. 2). SEM examination of valves showed that there was no central

Fig. 1. Map with location of Atlantic areas with *Pseudo-nitzschia australis* in spring 2010.

1) Bay of Brest. 2) Bay of Douarnenez.
3) "Pertuis Charentais".

(Cont'd on p. 2)

Fig. 2. Light micrographs of *Pseudo-nitzschia australis*. A) chain in valve view. B) same chain in girdle view showing large overlap of cells. Scale bars = 50 μm .

interspace (Fig. 3 A), and that interstriae and fibulae were usually distributed in equal numbers (12–14 in 10 μm). The striae were composed of two rows of poroids (4–5 in 1 μm) (Fig. 3B). Moreover, the valves were heteropolar (Fig. 3C & D). Otherwise, the structure of the girdle revealed the presence of three types of bands with 17–19 band striae in 10 μm (Fig. 3E). The identification of *P. australis* was thus confirmed, excluding the hypothesis of *P. seriata*, the closest congeneric species [5–6]. Molecular analysis (PCR amplification and sequencing) was undertaken on individual chains isolated from field samples. The two resulting ITS (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2) rDNA sequences were compared with other sequences of *Pseudo-nitzschia* available in GenBank. They were identical (100% similarity) with all ITS sequences of *P. australis* of both European and Californian origin (Table 1).

This unexpected outbreak happened after the “Xynthia” storm on the 28 february 2010 which severely affected the coasts of the “Pertuis Charentais”.

Table 1. List of ITS rDNA sequences of *Pseudo-nitzschia australis* available in GenBank and used for a comparison with our two studied isolates.

Accession number	Strain designation	Origin
AM118029	PLY1St.24D	Scotland
AM118030	PLY1St.27E	Scotland
AM118031	PLY1St.33A	Scotland
AM118032	PLY1St.37A	Scotland
AM118033	PLY1St.37B	Scotland
AM118034	PLY1St.54C	Scotland
AM118035	PLY1St.56B	Scotland
AM118036	PLY1St.68C	Scotland
AY257842	ØM1	Aveiro, Portugal
AY452527	PLYSt19A	Scotland
AY452528	PLYSt54B	Scotland
DQ062661	au43	Monterey Bay, California
EF564717	Paul	Bay of Seine, France
EU523100	C1	France
EU684233	Delta 2	Portugal

Many reared bivalves from this area were contaminated with high toxicity levels. At present, the degree of contamination of king scallops is unknown due to closure of the harvesting sites. But we can be anxious considering the kinetics of contamination and depuration of these shellfish.

Acknowledgements

We thank our colleagues Sylvie Genauzeau, Mireille Fortune and Jacky

Chauvin from coastal laboratories for providing field samples and Karine Chèze of the Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle of Concarneau for sequencing.

References

- Nézan E *et al* 2006. *Harmful Algae News* 31: 1–3
- Amzil Z *et al* 2001. *Toxicon* 39: 1245–1251
- Lundholm N *et al* 2003. *J Phycol* 39: 797–813
- Hasle GR 1965. *Skrift Norske Vidensk Akad* 18: 1–45
- Fehling J *et al* 2004. *J Phycol* 40: 622–630
- Hasle GR & Lundholm N 2005. *Phycologia* 44: 608–619

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Fig. 3. Scanning electron micrographs of *Pseudo-nitzschia australis*. A) Valve illustrating asymmetrical valve outline and absence of central interspace. B) Higher magnification of central part of valves showing the two rows of poroids per striae. C, D) same valve with apices exhibiting the heteropolarity. E) Detail of a girdle band. Scale bars = 20 μm (A), 2 μm (B), 1 μm (C-E).

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• Canada

Multi-species raphidophyte blooms in British Columbia coastal waters

The official records of major fish-killing blooms of *Heterosigma akashiwo* in British Columbia in the 1980s and 1990s did not include unidentified raphidophytes, but this did not mean that they were not present. Records of total phytoplankton species collected for the purpose of tracing water movements in the region [1] show that *Heterosigma* was often accompanied and sometimes outnumbered by one or more of three unidentified raphidophytes, inlet dwellers with a preference for water in the 10–15°C range. Two of them almost certainly belonged to the same unnamed genus and the third was a species of *Chattonella* morphologically similar to *C. marina* but with a different water temperature preference.

In the first week of October 1990, a bloom containing all four of them and two unidentified species of *Prymnesium* was blamed for severe losses of penned salmon at a B.C. Packers fish farm in Simoom Sound, off the southern end of Queen Charlotte Strait. On this occasion *Heterosigma* was outnumbered 100:1 by the larger of the unnamed raphidophytes, but there was no official report of the bloom because none of the probable causal organisms was a named toxic species. B.C. Packers had chosen this location in the hope that its cold water would prevent *Heterosigma* from forming a bloom. It did, but the one that took its place was just as bad, and meant that the fish farmers' options were even more limited than previously thought. The result of not reporting it was that the fish-killing *Chattonella* bloom at Grieg Seafood's salmon farm in Esperanza Inlet in September 2002 took the company completely by surprise. Another result was that it was automatically reported as *C. marina*, setting a new record for the area which had to be dropped after it was compared with drawings of the 1990 *Chattonella*. The latter is described here in enough detail and with enough additional information to upgrade it to *C. cf. minima*, and hopefully the two unnamed

raphidophytes are described well enough to be recognisable. Here are the toxic and suspected toxic flagellates found in the bloom, and their maximum concentrations in the samples:

Raphidophyte 1 = F.J.R. Taylor's undescribed chloromonad [2]	1.1×10^6 cells L ⁻¹
Raphidophyte 2	2.2×10^5 cells L ⁻¹
<i>Chattonella</i> cf. <i>minima</i> = <i>Chattonella</i> sp. [1]	2.0×10^4 cells L ⁻¹
<i>Prymnesium</i> spp.	5.5×10^4 cells L ⁻¹
<i>Heterosigma akashiwo</i>	9.7×10^3 cells L ⁻¹

Water temperature was 13°C and salinity 26 ppt when they were collected at the height of the bloom. With a total phytoplankton count of 2×10^6 cells L⁻¹, it was not a particularly heavy one. However, if all the above species were toxic to fish, the combination of different kinds of toxins would have had an exacerbatory effect (J.C. Green, pers. comm.) The cells were preserved in acid Lugol's iodine, and the illustration shows them as they appeared under phase contrast illumination, though internal detail is missing. The cells of Raphidophyte 2 from oceanic stations were more squat than those from coastal stations and are included. The scale is 1cm:10 µm.

The following descriptions are from light microscopy only:

Species 1 is Raphidophyte 1. Samples were sent to anyone in the area who might be able to identify it, but the live cells were very difficult to transport and mine had rounded off and lost their flagella. Having no culture facilities with which to revive them I had to rely heavily on a pers. comm. from Edward Black who had found strong similarities to the fish-killing Flagellate X [3–4]. A rumour that it was a new *Olisthodiscus* meant that it could be E.M. Hulbert's presumed brown *O. luteus* [5], and Hulbert's Fig. 3 closely resembles Droop's Fig. 5 #1 [3]. The cell length was ~18 µm in both cases. Reconstructing the collapsed cells of Raphidophyte 1 assuming the same degree of shrinkage as Raphidophyte 2, the live ones were no more than 23 µm.

The rounded live cells were dorso-ventrally flattened with 6–18 brownish-yellow, peripherally-arranged discoid chloroplasts and many peripheral extrusomes whose presence only became apparent when they discharged their contents. The unusual way that the cells collapsed in the fixative suggests that they had a posterior invagination. A posterior invagination like that of *Haramonas* would have been easy to miss.

When the rounded cells were examined under a coverslip, it was found that the extrusomes had discharged their contents in the form of discrete, slender threads. Edward Black, who had seen motile and non-motile cells with their extrusomes discharged, found similarities to drawings of Flagellate X in the same condition (Figs. 5 #2 & 3 in ref. 3; Fig. 3A in ref. 4).

Raphidophyte 1 was recorded from stations on Canadian Weathership Line P in the 1970s (Table 8 in ref. 6), and subsequently [1] from Saanich Inlet, Esquimalt Lagoon and offshore plumes from Barkley and Kyuquot Sounds. Its highest recorded concentration was 9.1×10^6 cells L⁻¹ in a Barkley Sound plume in July 1985, water temperature 14.4°C, salinity 31.5 ppt. Its recorded water temperature and salinity ranges were 9.5–15.5°C and 25.0–32.4 ppt.

Species 2 is Raphidophyte 2. F.J.R. Taylor and I had this species in culture in the 1970s, and a sketch of a live cell [6] shows that in ventral view it is bilaterally symmetrical and ovoid or sub-pyriform. It also shows what appears to be a posterior invagination. The cells had 4–6 brownish-yellow, discoid, non-overlapping, peripherally-arranged chloroplasts and many peripheral extrusomes which discharged their contents when a coverslip was applied. At first sight they looked like trichocysts, but they remained attached. The cells were dorso-ventrally flattened, 8–12 µm long, 6–9 µm wide, 4–5 µm thick, concave on the ventral face and convex

on the dorsal. Two sub-equal, heterodynamic flagella much longer than the cell arose from the ventral surface about a third of the way down from the anterior end. The swimming motion was a glide while slowly turning over and over, or maybe over and back again, with the longer flagellum extended forwards and the shorter one trailing. Asexual reproduction was by binary fission in the motile stage.

Raphidophyte 2 was recorded from coastal and oceanic stations on Line P in the 1970s (Table 8 in ref. 6), it was subsequently recorded [1] and in and off Barkley Sound, from Saanich Inlet and Esquimalt Lagoon, the coastal waters adjacent to Quatsino Sound, Nootka Sound and Esperanza Inlet, and from Hecate Strait and Station P. Its numbers at Station P were surprisingly high, up to 2×10^5 cells L^{-1} at a water temperature of $6.5^\circ C$. The highest concentration recorded was 1.4×10^6 cells L^{-1} in the mouth of an inlet on the west coast of Moresby Island in the Queen Charlottes in July 1983, water temperature $14^\circ C$, salinity 31.74 ppt. Its recorded water temperature and salinity ranges were $5.4\text{--}16.2^\circ C$ and 26.0–33.65 ppt.

Species 3 is *Chattonella* cf. *minima*. Until I saw it alive in 1990 I did not know what it was and recorded it as a raspberry shape (see also 7). The cells in the 1990 bloom were 20–55 μm long, and very variable in shape. The few fully motile cells in a live sample were 30–35 μm long and obovoid or oblong (cf. Hulbert's *O. magnus*). Most cells were globular (cf. Fig. 2(3) in ref. 7) and slow-moving or non-motile. The big round one in the drawing which appears to have burst open was fully intact but behaving like an amoeba, and as these cells deteriorated further they became plasmodial (cf. Fig. C of *C. globosa* in ref. 8; Fig. 3 in ref. 9). The motile cells had numerous brownish or greenish-gold ellipsoid chloroplasts sometimes situated just beneath the cell membrane. Their minimum and maximum dimensions were 1.5 and 3.4 μm , and their basal pyrenoids were just visible. There were numerous minute lipid globules immediately beneath the cell membrane, staining black in osmium tetroxide, and these

Fig. 1. Sketches of raphidophytes from British Columbia coastal waters.

were interspersed with spherical vesicles approximately 0.5–1.5 μm in diameter. When the cells lysed they became surrounded by many tiny fibrils, but there was no sign of mucocysts. Two sub-equal, heterodynamic flagella arose from an anterior depression which looked quite deep in the big globular cells. On the basis of detailed colour drawings and a photograph of the live cells, Y. Hara (pers. comm.) suggested that it was a type of *Chattonella* often seen in the Inland Sea of Japan when the water temperature was $10\text{--}15^\circ C$. He said that it was toxic to farmed yellowtail but did not form red tides, unlike *C. marina* which preferred $24\text{--}27^\circ C$ water, and that he was preparing its taxonomy for publication. It turned out that he was referring to *C. minima* [9], already provisionally named by Fukuyo *et al* [8].

Chattonella was recorded by A.G. Lewis and myself from Jervis Inlet in June 1977 (unpubl.) and later [1] in and off Barkley Sound and Kyuquot Inlet. The highest concentration found was in the 1990 bloom. It was seen less often than the other two raphidophytes,

possibly because it could not survive for long in the higher salinity water outside the inlets and only two of the cruises included an inlet. Its recorded water temperature and salinity ranges were $9.9\text{--}16.5^\circ C$ and 26.0–32 ppt.

Species 4 and 5 are *Prymnesium* spp. The larger one was yellow-brown and dorso-ventrally flattened, 16–24 μm long, and the other was brown and cylindrical, 11–17 μm long. The larger one was previously recorded from Esquimalt Lagoon and the smaller one off Barkley Sound [6]. They were rarely seen outside the inlets.

Species 6 is *Heterosigma akashiwo*. It was not always as easily distinguished from Raphidophyte 1 in Lugol samples as the illustration implies.

Raphidophytes 1 and 2 were found in good condition in the offshore plumes from the inlets. The plumes were known to have come from the inlets because they contained unusually high numbers of inshore algae such as *Tetraselmis* and *Eutreptiella*, and dead freshwater algae such as *Tabellaria* and *Scenedesmus*. The July 1985 Barkley Sound plume was a *Heterosigma* bloom containing high

numbers of Raphidophyte 1 (up to 3.9×10^7 cells L^{-1} and 9.1×10^6 cells L^{-1} , respectively). As this is quite a low ratio, it is likely that Raphidophyte 1 contributed to the fish-killing *Heterosigma* blooms in Barkley Sound from 1988 to 1990 [2]. The plume also contained the other two raphidophytes, and the four of them were there again in June, July and August 1986 and in a plume from Kyuquot Sound in August 1989. The full data [1], cover a water temperature range of 5.4–19.7°C, show that 7.2×10^4 cells L^{-1} was the recorded maximum for *Heterosigma* at or below a water temperature of 13 °C. They also show that Raphidophyte 1 can be

mistaken for *Heterosigma* in Lugol samples. In Waters *et al* [6], a combination of Lugol material and a mistranslation of German led to a complicated mix-up between the harmless *Cochlodinium citron* and the fish-killing *C. polykrikoides*. This was an avoidable mistake, but I hope that in the foregoing I have made a case for including pictures of Lugol's-preserved cells in guides to toxic flagellates.

References:

1. Forbes JR & RE Waters 1993. *Can Data Rep Hydrogr Ocean Sci* 117. Vol. 1 (1979–84): 212 pp, Vol. 2 (1985–89): 247 pp
2. Forbes JR (ed) 1991. *Can Tech Rep Hydrogr Ocean Sci* 135: 76pp

3. Tett P (ed) 1980. *Scottish Mar Biol Assoc Internal Report* 25
4. Gowen R & Lewis J 1982. *Scottish Mar Biol Assoc Internal Report* 71
5. Hulbert EM 1965. *J Phycol* 1: 87-94
6. Waters RE *et al* 1992. *Can Tech Rep Hydrogr Ocean Sci* 137: 59 pp
7. Band-Schmidt C *et al* 2005. *Harmful Algae News* 28: 6–7
8. Fukuyo Y *et al* (eds) 1990. *Red Tide Organisms in Japan - An Illustrated Taxonomic Guide*, Uchida Rokakuho, Tokyo, 430pp
9. Hara Y *et al* 1994. *Jap J Phycol* 42: 407–420

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Yasumoto honored by the University of Vigo

On January 28, 2010 at the University of Vigo, Spain, Professor Takeshi Yasumoto was given special recognition for his leadership in marine toxin research and his assistance to many countries over the years. Prof Yasumoto was awarded *Doctor Honoris Causa*, to recognize a deserving scientist who has devoted much of his life to the study of marine biotoxins, with an exemplary attitude of support and collaboration with many scientists worldwide. He was accompanied by his wife Tomiko and surrounded by many colleagues and friends, who came from many different countries to support him and

acknowledge his many contributions. The Ceremony was chaired by the University Rector, Professor Alberto Gago.

Professor José Antonio Rodríguez Vázquez, Director of the Analytical Chemistry Department at the University of Vigo, presented Professor Yasumoto as the most recognized scientist in the field of marine biotoxins. In this presentation Prof. Rodríguez-Vázquez summarized the intense activity of Professor Yasumoto in the field, spanning several aspects, from the identification of many new marine algal toxins, to providing toxin standards to laboratories around the world, and

assisting countries around the world to establish methods.

To further honour Professor Yasumoto, a seminar entitled: *Marine Toxins: Analysis and Toxicology* was chaired by Dr. Ana Gago-Martinez, Professor in the Department of Analytical and Food Chemistry at the University of Vigo and Director of the European Reference Laboratory of Marine Biotoxins. The seminar was held on January 29, the day after the *Honoris Causa* ceremony. In the Chair's introduction, she shared her experiences regarding the remarkable personality of Professor Yasumoto, both his personal warmth and his scientific excellence. Professor Gago-Martínez expanded on these aspects of Yasumoto's character through accounts of his other activities in the field of marine biotoxins, including his involvement and collaboration with different Institutions worldwide, in particular in Galicia (Prof Yasumoto has often described Galicia as his second home).

Included in the seminar programme were presentations by leading scientists in the marine biotoxin field who attended to honour Prof. Yasumoto on the occasion of his award and also to share their own knowledge and experience with other scientists. The Seminar covered several topics in the analytical and toxicological aspects of marine

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• Nicaragua

First report of PSP on Pacific coast of Nicaragua associated with *Pyrodinium bahamense*

Studies of marine phytoplankton and harmful algae on Nicaraguan coasts are very scarce. As historical antecedents, there were red tide alerts on the Pacific coasts of Guatemala and El Salvador in December 2000 and of Costa Rica in September 2001. During those events, the Nicaraguan health ministry (MINSa) detected neither red tides nor shellfish toxicity.

In early November 2005, reddish patches were seen off the north Pacific coast of Nicaragua, due to a bloom dominated by *Pyrodinium bahamense*. This event was associated with 50 cases of PSP toxicity, including one death, following consumption of mangrove cockles (*Anadara tuberculosa*).

This event had a strong economic impact in six municipalities (Corinto, El Realejo, Chinandega, El Norte Viejo, Posoltega and León) whose main sources of income are the harvesting and commercialization of molluscs. The health authorities sought help from the Nicaraguan Aquatic Resources Research Centre of the National Autonomous University in Managua (CIRA/UNAN), to identify the

Fig. 1. Sampling stations on Pacific coast of Nicaragua

phytoplankton species potentially responsible for the toxic outbreak.

Water samples for phytoplankton analysis were taken on 11 and 15 November 2005 at three coastal stations off Corinto (Chinandega) selected by MINSa (Fig. 1), at Paso Caballos (11 November) where the cases of poisoning occurred, and from two stations 7 and 11 miles from Corinto (15 November), where reddish patches had been seen the previous day during overflights. Oblique hauls for qualitative

analysis were taken with a 10 μm mesh net and transported to the laboratory live, quantitative samples with a 2.5 L van Dorn at 0.5 m depth, and fixed with Lugol's iodine. Counts were made with an Olympus CH40 inverted microscope following the Utermöhl method.

Both diatoms and dinoflagellates were common at the Paso Caballos and 11 mile stations, but the patch detected from the air the previous day was a practically monospecific bloom of *Pyrodinium*

bahamense (Fig. 1), which reached concentrations of 17.3×10^6 cell L^{-1} , compared with 72×10^3 cell L^{-1} and 14×10^3 cell L^{-1} at Paso Caballos and the 11 mile station respectively.

Epidemiological results are summarized in Fig. 2 and 3. Symptoms were muscular weakness (76%), oral numbness (56%), and vomiting (50%). Mouse bioassay indicated a maximum saxitoxin concentration of $1265 \mu\text{g STX eq } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$ of meat; toxicity was undetectable one month later.

Pyrodinium bahamense var. *compressum* (Fig. 4) is presently considered a harmful species in the tropics due to its high toxicity, and has been associated with intense episodes of PSP on the Pacific coast of Mexico and Central America which have included fatalities. In November 1989, 99 people were poisoned (three fatally) in the Gulf of Tehuantepec, Mexico [1]; 187 people (26 fatalities) were affected in July 1987 in Guatemala [2]. In El Salvador, between August 2001 and January 2002, there were 41 cases [3], and in Costa Rica, in 1999 and 2000, there were about 70 cases [4].

This is the first report of a PSP event in Nicaragua, accompanied by observations of plankton patches and standard methods of toxin analysis, identification of the suspect species, and a parallel epidemiological study coordinated by MINSa. This event indicates the need for a phytoplankton

Fig. 2. Percentage contributions and numerical abundance of phytoplankton groups at the three stations

Fig. 3. Percentages of different symptoms in people poisoned, temporal distribution of cases and saxitoxin levels ($\mu\text{g equiv. STX} \cdot 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$ of meat) estimated by mouse bioassay in *Anadara tuberculosa* during toxic event on Pacific coast Nicaragua, November 2005. (Data of SILAIS, Sistema Local de Atención Integral de Salud).

monitoring program on the Pacific coast of Nicaragua, and for testing toxicity in shellfish destined for human consumption. This type of program would prevent the occurrence of human poisoning, identify periods and zones at risk, and mitigate economic losses to the mariculture industry.

There is also a need to establish links for technical cooperation and information exchange among Central American countries, especially those which share common *P. bahamense* events. It is possible that blooms of *P. bahamense* reflect mesoscale events over a wide zone of Pacific Central America, and that a communication network between countries affected would improve prediction of the development of these events, and improve the analytical capacity of national laboratories responsible for toxin detection and phytoplankton taxonomy.

Finally, it is of great importance that consumers be informed of the risks associated with shellfish consumption

exposed to these toxins by the state institutions (INETER; ADPESCA) to deal with the problem in a coordinated manner.

References:

1. Cortés-Altamirano R *et al* 1993. 2^o Congreso de Ciencias del Mar, La Habana, Cuba
2. Rosales-Loessener F 1989. In Hallegraeff GM & JL Maclean (eds), *Biology, Epidemiology and Management of Pyrodinium Red Tides* (ICLARM), 49–51
3. Barraza JE *et al* 2004. Rev Biol Trop 52: 1–4

4. Vargas-Montero M & Freer E 2002. Xth International Conference St. Pete's Beach, Florida, USA. October 21–25

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Fig. 4. Photograph of *Pyrodinium bahamense* (40x and 10x).

Alexandrium catenella during 2009 in Chilean waters, and recent expansion to coastal ocean

In Chile, historical data show that blooms of the toxic dinoflagellate *Alexandrium catenella* have increased in frequency, duration, extent and intensity in recent decades [1–2]. In 1972, *A. catenella* was recorded in Estrecho de Magallanes for the first time [3]. Subsequently, in 1981 a new bloom of this species was described in the Magallanes region [4]. The first record of the species in Churrecua Island, Region XI, was in 1992 [5].

The presence of this paralytic shellfish poison (PSP) producer was first detected in Region X in quantitative samples between January and June 2002; it caused an intense bloom which covered a wide area of the Chiloé Archipelago. This outbreak occurred off Quellón, Cailín Island, including Guapiquilán, in the southern part of the Chiloé archipelago, and lasted from 22 January 2002 to April of the same year; it advanced northwards and reached Dalcahue channel [2]. Since then, *A. catenella* has recurred off Chiloe Island in the years 2003, 2004, 2005, 2006 and 2009.

A. catenella outbreak 2009

The 2009 outbreak has been one of the most important in terms of abundance and distribution. The outbreak covered a wide geographical area from 46° to 43° 45' S during the first half of March [2] (Fig. 1). *A. catenella* cells were first detected on 15 January in the Izaza area (44° 34' S), King Channel. For several weeks, cell concentrations did not exceed 40 cells mL⁻¹, until 23 February when the first major outbreak was detected off Ester Island (45° 09' S), reaching a maximum of 2230 cells mL⁻¹ to a depth of 5 m. Later, from 4 to 10 March, the dinoflagellate reached maximum abundance, and we observed several peaks in the area of the Guaitecas archipelago, reaching concentrations of 1200, 1500, 1800, 3000 and exceeding 6000 cells mL⁻¹ in the areas of Cuptana (44° 32' S), Canalad (44° 33' S), Angostura (45° 36' S), Ester (45° 09' S) and Allan (45° 45' S), respectively (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Distribution of *A. catenella* during 2009.

During this period, the high cell concentrations generated intense reddish discoloration of the water, and bioluminescence, with cell chains that were visible to the naked eye due to their long length (Fig. 2a).

Recent expansion of *A. catenella*

During the first fifteen days of March 2009, *A. catenella* was detected only in the Guaitecas south area (43° 50' S), but on 17 March 2009 it occurred off Chiloé Island, Laitec zone (43° 13' S) where it persisted until April 15; it was next detected off central Chiloé, in Lincay zone (42° 38' S) and then further

north in Huyar, Quinchao Island (42° 23' S) on July 6.

Prior to 2009, *A. catenella* was confined to the northern edge of the Chiloé inland sea [2]; it was found in net samples (23 µm) in the Faro Corona area northwest of Chiloe on 30 Oct 2009, and in Mar Brava and Cucao areas on 3 and 4 Nov 2009 respectively.

This report of *A. catenella* is important due to the following issues;

- it shows a northward expansion of the species range
- it is the first record of the species in SE Pacific coastal oceanic waters, off Chiloé Island.

Fig. 2. Images of *A. catenella*. Ester Island Summer 2009. a) Assemblage in a laboratory flask, ca. 4500 cell mL⁻¹. (photo: E. Minte). b) *A. catenella* chain of 52 cells (photo: J. Mardones).

This new distribution of *A. catenella* suggests cell transport to inland waters through the Chacao Channel. Cells can reach Chiloé waters and further north, not only from the fjords and channels south of 43° S, but also from water masses of coastal oceanic origin.

On 4 Nov 2009, *A. catenella* was detected in Punta Bonita (41° 44' S) Calbuco area; this is the most northerly record of the species so far. During this period, *A. catenella* was not observed off the northeast coast of Chiloé Island, suggesting that these cells reached the

area via the Chacao channel, in agreement with previous records of the species in the Mar Brava and Faro Corona areas (Fig. 1).

We thank Instituto Tecnológico del Salmón (INTESAL) for data support.

References:

1. Guzmán L *et al* 2002. In Sar E *et al* (eds), *Floraciones Algaes Nocivas en el Cono Sur Americano*: 235–255
2. Clément A *et al* 2009. Simposio de Microalgas, XXIX Congreso de Ciencias del Mar, p 80.
3. Guzmán L & Campodonico I 1975. *Monografías del Instituto de la Patagonia* 9: 44 pp
4. Lembeye G 1981. *An Inst Patagon* 12: 273–276, 277–288
5. Muñoz P *et al* 1992. *Rev Biol Mar* 27: 187–212

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New manual available

Microscopic and molecular methods for quantitative phytoplankton analysis

A new manual on microscopic and molecular methods for quantitative phytoplankton analysis is available from the IOC in cooperation with ICES. The manual includes illustrated step by step instructions on how to carry out the methods. The manual can be downloaded as a pdf-file from www.ioc-unesco.org/hab.

The manual complements the existing IOC Manual on Harmful Marine Microalgae published in 2003.

Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of ©UNESCO. 2010. Karlson, B., Cusack, C. and Bresnan, E. (editors). Microscopic and molecular methods for quantitative phytoplankton analysis. Paris, UNESCO. (IOC Manuals and Guides, no. 55.) (IOC/2010/MG/55), 110 pages.(English only)

Dinoflagellate blooms in eutrophic zones of Bahía de Cienfuegos, Cuba

In recent years, increasing supplies of nutrients to water bodies by human activities has been associated with growth in the predominance of algal blooms. Increased nutrient fluxes to estuarine and coastal areas result from agriculture, aquaculture, and discharges of industrial and domestic wastes. The resulting blooms lead to hypoxia, fish mortalities, toxicity of food organisms, and damage to benthic communities resulting from reduced light penetration and resulting alterations in trophic interactions throughout the ecosystem [1].

Bahía de Cienfuegos, one of the most valuable natural resources of the province of the same name, is distinguished by its extent and its beauty (Fig. 1). The variety of developments in the surroundings and exploitation of the bay itself have impacted both the water and the coastal zone, and for these reasons it has been chosen for study within the framework of the Ramal Scientific-Technical Program, "Cuban Environmental Protection and Sustainable Development". Estimates indicate that direct nutrient discharges from urban areas contribute 15,1% to the total discharges from the river

systems [2].

At the beginning of the rainy season, July 2009, about 50 to 100 dead fish were observed near domestic waste discharged from Cienfuegos city, near station 12 (Fig. 1). According to local dock-workers, the fish had reached the shore showing signs of lack of oxygen, and red patches had been seen repeatedly that week.

The monitoring the day after showed these coincided with blooms of *Heterocapsa*. Cell shape and the position of the nucleus and pyrenoid coincide with the description of *H. circularisquama* [3]. The patch covered about 500 m².

Heterocapsa circularisquama has caused mass mortalities of bivalves in Japan [4]. Cells of this dinoflagellate

Fig. 1. Bahía de Cienfuegos. State monitoring network. Arrows show main discharge zones of domestic and industrial wastes.

were abundant in the fishes gills, but cells of the benthic *Amphidinium* cf. *carterae* (Fig. 3), which produces haemolytic ichthyotoxins, were also found there. *A. cf. carterae* was present in the plankton samples, but in low concentrations. Its presence in the gills might indicate that it was relatively abundant in the nearby benthos. One other benthic species, *Prorocentrum rathymum*, also appeared in moderate numbers in the plankton samples. In the areas close to the domestic discharges, substrates for benthic microflora are abundant, with flourishing filamentous macroalgae and hydrozoans, and carpets of cyanobacteria, most of them toxic.

Meteorological conditions at the time were calm with high air temperatures (35–36° C) typical of summer in Cuba, and scarce rainfall.

Other toxic or noxious species (Fig. 4) have been seen accompanying blooms in other parts of the bay, and seem to be established components of the microflora here. Amongst these are *Gymnodinium* cf. *catenatum*, a potential source of paralytic toxins, *Cochlodinium* cf. *polykrikoides* with ichthyotoxic properties, *Dinophysis caudata* and *D. ovum*, producers of

Fig. 2. *Heterocapsa cf. circularisquama* in Lugo preserved sample. Arrows indicate location of pyrenoid.

Fig. 3. *Amphidinium cf. carterae*

diarrhetic toxins, *Prorocentrum minimum*, producer of neurotoxins, and *Gonyaulax polygramma* y *G. spinifera*, associated with ichthyotoxic events.

Blooms of nontoxic dinoflagellates also occur, mainly at the end of the dry season and beginning of the rainy season, when temperatures increase. These include *Gyrodinium instriatum*, *Gymnodinium estuariale*, *Peridinium quinquecorne* and *Prorocentrum compressum* (Fig. 5) close to stations 10 and 12, contributing to decline of the density and biomass of *Halodule wrightii*, the most abundant phanerogam in the bay, as well as the large rhodophytes (*Gracilaria*, *Acanthophora*, *Hypnea*) typical of this ecosystem. Blooms of *Gymnodinium estuariale* close to the outlet of the River Salado and near the industrial sector

Fig. 4. Other toxic or noxious species associated with blooms in waste discharge areas; A) *Gymnodinium cf. catenatum*, B) *Cochlodinium cf. polykrikoides*, C) *Dinophysis caudata*, D) *D. ovum*, E) *Gonyaulax polygramma*, F) *G. spinifera*, G) *Prorocentrum rhathymum*, H) *P. minimum*

(stations 8 and 9) increase chlorophyll *a* concentrations up to $38.17 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. These blooms of nontoxic dinoflagellates and the abundant epiphytes of the filamentous macroalgae and hydrozoans reduce light levels in the marine meadows and lead to their deterioration.

Acknowledgements

To the HAB ProgramA1 (COI-UNESCO) and the OIEA project on

toxic algal blooms in the Caribbean region (ARCAL RLA, 7/014), and to Carlos Alonso and the CEAC laboratory.

References:

1. GEOHAB 2006. *Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms, Harmful Algal Blooms in Eutrophic Systems*. P. Gilbert (ed), IOC-SCOR
2. Seisdedo y Arencibia 2009. *Rev Transporte, Medio Ambiente y Desarrollo* No. 2-3 (in press)
3. Iwataki M 2008. *Plankton Benthos Res* 3: 135-142
4. Horiguchi T 1995. *Phycol Res* 43: 129-136

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Fig. 5. Nontoxic species which form blooms in discharge areas; A. *Prorocentrum compressum*, B. *Peridinium quinquecorne*, C. *Gymnodinium estuariale*, D. *Gyrodinium instriatum*

Harmful Algae News

Previous issues of HAN and newsletters of the IOC HAB Programme can be downloaded at <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/news.htm>

Requests for subscription

Subscription to HAN is made by sending a request with a complete address to Ms V. Bonnet: v.bonnet@unesco.org.

Prorocentrum levis and *Coolia monotis* in Abruzzo coastal waters (W Adriatic)

The first appearance of *Prorocentrum lima* (Ehrenberg) Dodge in Abruzzo coastal waters (Western Adriatic) was reported in 2007 [1]. The ichthyotoxic *Fibrocapsa japonica* had been detected earlier [2]. Since then, other allochthonous toxic microalgal species have been observed, such as *Ostreopsis cf. ovata* in summer 2008 [3], and *Prorocentrum levis* and *Coolia monotis* in 2009. These investigations were carried out in four areas, harbours and rocky banks during June, July, August and September 2007, 2008 and 2009 (Fig. 1).

These species are known to produce toxins that can be dangerous for human health. *F. japonica* produces neurotoxic (fibrocapsin), haemolytic, haemo-agglutinating compounds and oxygen radicals. The high toxicity of *F. japonica* is proposed to result from the production of a secondary metabolite named fibrocapsin [4]. It was described in detail and named by Toriumi and Takano in 1973 after dangerous blooms along Japanese coasts [5]. *P. lima* produces DSP toxins (Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning) that can contaminate filter-feeding shellfish and cause gastrointestinal illness in humans

[6]. The complex of DSP toxins produced by *P. lima* includes okadaic acid (OA), dinophysistoxins (DTX-1, DTX-2), prorocentrolide and fast acting toxin [7]: this species is distributed worldwide, often associated with coral reefs, or attached to floating detritus in mangrove habitats [8].

Ostreopsis ovata produces palytoxin-like compounds [9]. The production of putative palytoxin with other palytoxin-like compounds by *O. ovata* from Italy has recently been confirmed [10]: this species has generally been associated with tropical areas but has recently become relevant in temperate climates, including the Mediterranean Sea [11].

Prorocentrum levis was first isolated in 2002 from the Belize barrier reef system [12]: it was initially confused with *Prorocentrum concavum*. Its populations are often associated with floating mangrove detritus and sediments. The first report of this species in the Mediterranean, in 2004, was from Greek waters [13]. It was first reported in the Adriatic in 2006 [14], and on the Abruzzo coast in summer 2009. *P. levis* is considered toxic and produce DSP toxins okadaic acid and DTX2 [12].

P. levis is photosynthetic with brown-golden chloroplasts (Fig. 2a). Cells in culture forms chains, as also described by Aligizaki [13], of two to many cells, usually in hyaline envelopes. In culture, it forms spots attached to the flask walls (Fig. 2b). Cells measured 44 μm in length and 37 μm in width, a length to width ratio of 1.17 ($n = 20$) (Fig. 2c). The periplagellar area of the right valve is shallow depressed, bearing about eight platelets (Figs. 2d and 2e).

Coolia monotis is considered toxic [15] and produces cooliatoxin, a neurotoxic analog of yessotoxin [16]; it has been found in plankton from brackish habitats and tidal pools, as well as mangrove environments. This species is most common in warm shallow waters of the Caribbean Sea and the Pacific Ocean [17], but during the last decade, has been reported from the Mediterranean [18]. In the Adriatic, this species has been observed in the Gulf of Trieste [19] and Conero Riviera [20] and now on the Abruzzo coast (summer 2009). *Coolia monotis* is a planktonic, benthic and epiphytic species [21]; it is photosynthetic, with many golden-brown discoid chloroplasts. The cells are compressed, round and lens-shaped. Cells measured 36 μm in length and 35 μm in trans-diameter ($n = 20$) (Fig. 3a). The cingulum is equatorial, narrow, and enclosed by lists with a smooth edge (Fig. 3b). The sulcus is narrow with a deep chamber-like appearance with straight walls (Fig. 3c). The apical pore plate, Po, is located off-center on epitheca (Fig. 3d).

In this study, four confined areas were monitored during the summers 2007, 2008 and 2009: Pescara harbour; Ortona harbour; San Vito and Fossacesia rocky point respectively. These stations were selected to localize epiphytic species like *P. lima*, *C. monotis*, *O. ovata* and *P. levis* since they live on macroalgae, on sediments and in stagnant environments. Chemical - physical parameters of seawater were measured to understand their relationship with the presence/absence of tropical harmful species. At each

Fig. 1. Research Area.

Fig. 2. Light microscopy photographs of *Prorocentrum levis* at 1000x magnification scale bar = 10 μm : a) single cell with a centrally located pyrenoid and golden brown chloroplasts; b) Cells in chains stick on Petri plate. Scanning electron micrographs of *P. levis* from isolated strain; c) Left valve, scale bar = 20 μm ; d) The periflagellar area of the right valve is shallow depressed with pore along the valve margin, scale bar 20 μm ; e) bearing about eight platelets, scale bar 5 μm .

station, one seawater sample was taken at 0.5 m below the surface with a pump. Cell concentrations are expressed as cells L^{-1} , reading the entire well using a volume of 50 mL.

Algae observations were effected by the use of the light microscope (ausJENA Telaval 3) at 200x, 400x and 1000x magnification. For taxonomic determination and plate tabulation of *O. ovata* and *Coolia monotis* it was used a light microscope epifluorescent using a Zeiss Axiophot microscope at 200x, 400x and 1000x magnification following the Calcofluor method of Fritz & Triemer, 1985 using fluorescent brightener 28 (Sigma – Aldrich). For SEM analysis of *O. cf. ovata*, *P. lima*, *Coolia monotis* and *Prorocentrum levis* isolated cultures, cells were fixed in 4% formaldehyde. After stored for three days at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, cells were washed three time into distilled water eliminating the supernatant at each washing. They were successively dehydrated in alcohol series up to 100%, dried with CO_2 critical point (CPD), sputter coated with Au/Pd and examined on Philips XL–30–

CP electron microscope according to Zingone *et al.* 1990.

F. japonica has always been detected for the entire period of monitoring with a bloom phenomenon on August 2009 along the entire coast of study (7.1×10^5 cells L^{-1} mean abundances; 24 ± 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ mean water temperatures).

The first appearance of *P. lima*, instead, was recorded on summer 2007 inside Ortona harbor. Its cellular abundance has been detected for the entire season (June, July, August and September) with a mean concentration of 1.9×10^5 cells L^{-1} . During summers 2008 and 2009 *P. lima* was revealed not only at Ortona harbor but also at San Vito rocky bank, with mean concentrations of 6.9×10^3 cells L^{-1} .

The first appearance of *O. cf. ovata* was at the end of August 2008 at Ortona harbor and Fossacesia rocky bank. Its mean abundance was 3.6×10^3 cells L^{-1} (28 ± 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ mean water temperatures), while on summer 2009 (at the beginning of September) it was recorded also at San Vito rocky bank (1.5×10^3 cells L^{-1} mean concentrations).

Fig. 3. a) Light microscopy photographs of *Coolia monotis*. Cells are round and lens-shaped with many golden-brown discoid chloroplasts, 1000x magnification scale bar = 10 μm . LM epifluorescence of *C. monotis*, 1000x magnification scale bar = 10 μm ; b) Ventral and dorsal view of the cells where it is possible to observe the equatorial cingulum and narrow, and c) deep sulcus. Scanning electron micrographs of *C. monotis* from isolated strain d) Dorsal view with apical pore plate *Po* on epitheca (white arrow), scale bar = 10 μm .

P. levis and *C. monotis*, at last, have been detected for the first time during this last summer (August and September 2009) only at Ortona harbor, with 1.5×10^3 and 3.0×10^2 cells L^{-1} mean concentrations respectively.

The increase of sea water temperature and the expand of ships traffic and their ballast waters have caused the entry of several tropical harmful microalgae. In fact, the Ortona harbor point, characterized by a major ship traffic, has revealed the entire community of the species in study among the four sampling stations. Besides, the highest temperature values of the three years of monitoring were always measured on August. During these periods, the greatest contemporary presence of the harmful species has been registered. As a matter of fact, water temperature trend has been positively correlated with harmful algae abundances ($p = 0.001$; $n = 96$).

Acknowledgements

We sincerely thank Dr. Stefano

Teodori and Dr. Antonio Teodori for help and councils; Sebastiano Di Bucchianico for informations provided.

References:

1. Ingarao C *et al* 2009. *Mar Pollut Bull* 58: 596–600
2. Pistocchi R *et al* 2008. SBI (Italian Society of Botany) *Abstract Acts*.
3. Ingarao C *et al* 2008. *Harmful Algae News* 39: 4–5
4. Khan S *et al* 1996. *J World Aquacult Soc* 27: 254–263
5. Toriumi S & Takano H 1973. *Bull Tokai Reg Fish Res Lab* 76: 25–35
6. Quilliam MA & Wright JLC 1995. *In Manual on Harmful Marine Microalgae. IOC Manuals and Guides n° 33, UNESCO, Paris: 95–111*
7. Moestrup Ø *et al* 2004. IOC Taxonomic Reference List of Toxic Algae. IOC of UNESCO. ioc.unesco.org/hab/data.htm, 2004
8. Fukuyo Y 1981. *Bull Jpn Soc Sci Fish* 47(8): 967–978
9. Ciminiello P *et al* 2006. *Anal Chem* 78: 6153–6159
10. Ciminiello P *et al* 2008. *J Am Soc Mass Spectrom* 19: 111–120
11. Mangialajo L *et al* 2008. *Mar Pollut Bull* 56: 1209–1214
12. Faust, M.A. 2008. *J. Phycol.* 44: 232–240
13. Aligizaki, K. *et al* 2009. *Harmful Algae*: 299–311
14. Honsell G *et al* 2008. SBI (Italian Society of Botany) *Abstract Acts*
15. Nakajima I *et al* 1981. *Bull Jpn Soc Sci Fish*

47: 1029–1033

16. Holmes MJ *et al* 1995. *Nat Tox* 3: 355–362
17. Faust MA 1992. *J Phycol* 28: 94–104
18. Vila M *et al* 2001. *Aquat Microb Ecol* 26: 51–60
19. Monti M *et al* 2007. *Mar Pollut Bull* 54: 598–601
20. Totti C *et al* 2007. *Harmful Algae News* 33: 12–13
21. Steidinger KA & Tangen K 1996. *In* Tomas, CR (ed) Identifying marine diatoms and dinoflagellates. *Academic Press*. 598 pp

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GEOHAB updates and news

The *GEOHAB Implementation Plan* (GEOHAB, 2003) specifies the formation of Core Research Projects (CRPs) related to four ecosystems types: upwelling systems, fjords and coastal embayments, eutrophic systems and stratified systems. In 2010, a fifth working group will be initiated, on Benthic HABs. These CRPs are initiated through small, focused open science meetings. GEOHAB also supports infrastructure activities, including development of modeling, and interaction with other international efforts such as the International Ocean Colour Coordinating Group (IOCCG). GEOHAB has made significant progress in many of these core areas, as highlighted below.

New GEOHAB Release—Fjords & Coastal Embayments

Harmful algal blooms are a frequent and important problem in coastal environments, particularly in fjords, inlets and embayments where conditions for

growth are often favorable (cell retention, availability of nutrients, etc.). Recognizing this, SCOR and IOC's International Programme on Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms, GEOHAB, supported an Ocean Sciences Meeting in Viña del Mar (Chile), to foster the development of international collaboration on this topic. The Report of this Meeting has now been published as GEOHAB's Report n°. 6, entitled "GEOHAB 2010. Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms, GEOHAB Core Research Project: HABs in Fjords and Coastal Embayments", edited by Allan Cembella, Leonardo Guzmán, Suzanne Roy and Jorge Diogène. It is available on the Web at www.geohab.info, or by contacting Ed Urban (Ed.Urban@scor-int.org) or Henrik Enevoldsen (h.enevoldsen@unesco.org). This Report contains six major sections that describe the GEOHAB approach, an overview of harmful algal blooms in fjords and coastal embayments, the

identification of research priorities, a description of framework activities and a list of planned activities. Seven key questions have been highlighted, including adaptive strategies that characterize HAB species in these environments, the importance of life history transitions and cysts, the role of physical dispersion and aggregation, the relative contribution of nutrient flux and supply ratios to HAB dynamics, the importance of spatial scale and retention time in the expression and effects of allelochemicals, and the effects of anthropogenic activities (e.g. aquaculture or ship transport through ballast water) and of global climate change on the dynamics of harmful algae in embayments and fjords.

New GEOHAB Release—GEOHAB Asia

Harmful algal blooms pose serious impacts on both coastal ecosystems and human activities in Asia, including aquaculture, public health and coastal

management, and damages caused by blooming of these species lead to huge economic losses. Frequency and severity of HAB events are increasing, and furthermore, their distribution within the region appears to be expanding. In this situation, the importance of exchange of information and cooperative research is a priority for researchers and managers working on HABs in Asia. In this context, two Asian GEOHAB Meetings were held, the first one in Tokyo, Japan in 2007, and the second one in Nha Trang, Vietnam in 2008. During the both meetings, the importance and usefulness of the comparative ecosystem approach were well recognized. The Report of these two meetings has now been published as GEOHAB's Report no. 7, entitled "GEOHAB 2010. Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms, Harmful Algal Blooms in Asia", edited by Ken Furuya, Patricia M. Glibert, Mingjiang Zhou and Robin Raine. It is available on the Web at www.geohab.info, or by contacting Ed Urban (Ed.Urban@scor-int.org) or Henrik Enevoldsen (h.enevoldsen@unesco.org). This Report contains five major sections: 1) an introduction on the process of developing GEOHAB Asia, 2) an overview of Asian HAB problems, 3) regional background and challenges for advancing the understanding of Asian HABs, 4) implementation of GEOHAB Asia following GEOHAB programme elements, and 5) programme advancement and capacity building. Key objectives and many questions have been highlighted for national and regional research in Asia, and targeted HAB species identified for co-operative comparative studies in GEOHAB Asia are suggested.

GEOHAB Special Issue in the journal Progress in Oceanography

The Canary, California, Humbolt and Benguela comprise the main eastern boundary upwelling systems of the world. Located on the western margins of continents, on each side of the equator, trade winds combined with the rotation of the earth generate coastal upwelling, bringing nutrient-rich water to the surface, thereby fueling high primary productivity. These upwelling

systems are susceptible to Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) owing largely to this high productivity and the consequent high biomass blooms characteristic of these environments. This special issue of *Progress in Oceanography*, dedicated to HABs in eastern boundary upwelling systems, is an outcome of the scientific programme GEOHAB initiated by SCOR and the IOC to foster international co-operative research on HABs in ecosystem types sharing common features (GEOHAB, 2001). Based on the knowledge and understanding of HABs as presented at the Open Science Meeting, eight key questions were developed to provide research foci for the Core Research Project. These key questions were to address the adaptive strategies of HAB species within upwelling systems, specifically their seeding strategies; the role of small-scale physical processes, and the influence of nutrient type and ratios on the growth and dispersion of HABs; the role of genetic predisposition versus environmental conditions in toxin production for a given genus or species; the importance of coastal morphology and bathymetry, and across-shelf and alongshore advection in the development and distribution of blooms; and the use of climate indicators as predictors of HAB events in upwelling systems (GEOHAB, 2005). This series of review papers, edited by Grant Pitcher and Stan Pillar, provides a comparative assessment and update of the status of our knowledge of HABs in upwelling systems and also serves as a measure of our progress in addressing the above questions formulated at the Open Science Meeting in 2003.

GEOHAB Special Issue in Journal of Marine Systems

The GEOHAB Science Plan defines Observation, Modelling and Prediction as one of GEOHAB's five central elements. To foster better integration of modeling efforts within GEOHAB and its Core Research Projects, a Modeling Workshop was held on 15-19 June 2009 at the Martin Ryan Institute, National University of Ireland. Primary objectives included stimulation of modeling activity in GEOHAB Core Research Projects; engagement of researchers, particularly students, in HAB modeling; improve

understanding of HAB processes through linkage of models, *in situ* observations, and remote sensing; and integration of HAB modeling and monitoring with the broader community of biogeochemical, population dynamics, and ecosystem modeling. Primary outcomes from this workshop include the forthcoming publication of both a GEOHAB report and a special issue devoted to HAB modeling in the *Journal of Marine Systems*.

New Working Group on HABs and Ocean Colour

The International Ocean Colour Coordinating Group (IOCCG) and GEOHAB have initiated an international working group on harmful algal blooms and ocean colour. The group will provide a guide to ocean colour-based harmful algal bloom methods, summarising the state of knowledge with regard to research and operational applications. Case studies from around the globe will be used to examine best-practice ocean colour application to harmful algal bloom observation across a variety of ecosystems. There will be a strong "consumer guide" focus: identifying uncertainties associated with ocean colour applications in the optically complex coastal zone; contextualising application with regard to the ecological role of potentially harmful algal blooms in different ecosystem types; and examination of the suitability of available ocean colour techniques within an ecosystem framework. The group will be composed of international ocean colour and harmful algal bloom scientists, and will begin work with a meeting in Cape Town in the third quarter of 2010. The working group convener is Stewart Bernard from the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research in South Africa.

• Mexico

Karenia sp. “Mexican hat” first bloom in Mexico

On 2 January 2010, north of the port of Veracruz, Mexico, large amounts of beached dead fish were reported by fishermen. Some water samples were obtained from the sea in front of this site to investigate if a HAB was the cause of the mortality. *Karenia* spp. were found in high concentrations.

Historically, Veracruz has suffered from HAB events for at least two centuries. The first record for fish kills dates back to 1797, and *K. brevis* was later thought to be the causative agent [1]. This species is known to be toxic and brevetoxins have been detected in molluscs from Veracruz [2–3]. The last two records of HAB events in the State of Veracruz, namely, in the vicinity of the port of Veracruz, were in 2001–2002 and 2003. In December 2001–January 2002, cell densities reached 2.3×10^7 cells L^{-1} [4]. In August 2003, cell densities were 5.0×10^4 cells L^{-1} [5]. Since then, no occurrence of HABs caused by this species has been recorded.

In the period 2003 to 2009, numerous blooms (more than 50) occurred near the port of Veracruz, and the non-toxic dinoflagellate *Peridinium quinquecorne* was found to be responsible [6]; this species was recorded as the cause of a HAB for the first time in 2002 [7]. A few diatom blooms have also occurred, mainly of *Chaetoceros* spp. (especially, *C. curvisetus*) and *Thalassiosira* spp. Several *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp., including potentially toxic ones, have been detected in high concentrations in samples from the National Park Sistema Arrecifal Veracruzano, the

Fig. 1. Red circle indicates location of a HAB event in early January 2010.

zone lying in front of the port. The filamentous cyanobacterium *Trichodesmium erythraeum* formed a bloom in October 2007 [8], and more recently has been observed forming blooms in coastal Veracruz waters.

To date, more than a dozen species of *Karenia* have been described. The formally described species of *Karenia* occurring in the Gulf of Mexico are as follows: *K. brevis*, *K. mikimotoi*, *K. papilionacea*, *K. selliformis*, and *K. cf. longicanalis*. Four of these can be separated molecularly, but all five can be morphologically differentiated even in fixed samples. In addition, other morphologically distinct unnamed *Karenia* species are known to inhabit the Gulf waters [9–10]. One of them is characterized by having a carina in form of a “sombbrero” and it is known as “Mexican hat” [10–11].

Microscopic analysis of two surface samples taken near Playa Norte, $19^{\circ} 15' 25.38''$ N, $96^{\circ} 11' 54.7''$ W (Fig. 1) revealed 92% by cell counts of *Karenia* sp. “Mexican hat” (Fig. 2) and 8% of *K. brevis* (Fig. 3) on January 2, and around 50% of each on January 4. The cells of *Karenia* sp. ranged from 20.5 to 32.5 μm (26.0 ± 2.4 ; $n = 180$) in length (L), from 27.5 to 45.0 μm (34.55 ± 4.23 ; $n = 224$) in width (W), from 15.0 to 20.0 μm (17.47 ± 1.34 ; $n = 22$) in depth (D), W/L ratio (1.32 ± 0.11 ; $n =$

177), W/D ratio (2.01 ± 0.19 ; $n = 22$). The nucleus is located in the low left hypotheca, closer to the centre of the cell. The carina is prominent in most cells, always slightly tilted to the left, and its sides are angular (in ventral-dorsal view, the line between the shoulders and the carina are even more pronounced due to the curvature of the right and left ventral lobes of the epitheca. Numerous peripheral chloroplasts (about 15–20) were clearly seen only in understained cells. In general, our cells correspond very well with the photograph of a cell collected in the northern Gulf of Mexico [9]. In contrast, *K. brevis* cells were smaller and less compressed anterior-posteriorly. The measurements were as follows: 21.0 – 30.0 μm (24.98 ± 2.05) length, 22.5 – 35.0 μm (26.12 ± 2.70) width, W/L ratio (1.01 ± 0.22) ($n = 29$). Statistical differences were significant in length and width between the species

Fig. 2. *Karenia* sp. “Mexican hat”.

Fig. 3. *Karenia brevis*.

Fig. 4. Mean values of length and width of *Karenia brevis* and *Karenia sp.* "Mexican hat". Boxes represent standard error, and whiskers show 0.95 confidence intervals.

($F = 5.14$, $p = 0.024$; $F = 108.7$, $p < 0.005$), so in addition to shape, they can be separated by size (Fig. 4).

We do not know exactly when the mixed bloom event of these two *Karenia* species began, but fishermen reported they had seen dead fish in the sea since 20 December 2009. The HAB was not visually evident until the dead fish were cast on the beach on January 2 (water temperature was 19°C). Fishermen reported they had experienced eye and respiratory irritation during the sampling period. Our count of *Karenia* that day was 1.17×10^5 cells L^{-1} , a high concentration for this taxon, considering that species of the genus had rarely been found in phytoplankton samples since 2003 in the State of Veracruz. Another phytoplankton sample obtained from the same site on January 4 was dominated by the diatom *Asterionellopsis glacialis* (1.16×10^5 cells L^{-1}), with *Karenia* still in high concentration (5.6×10^4 cells L^{-1}). This suggests that the *Karenia* HAB was ending when we detected the bloom.

According to the Sanitary Department of the State of Veracruz, almost one ton of dead fish was recorded. We estimated dead fish concentrations of up to 7 individuals m^{-2} . Scaridae (herbivores; especially, redbtail parrotfish *Sparisoma chrysopterum*) dominated. Among others, the following taxa were identified: Atlantic thread herring *Opisthonema* sp. (planktivore), red or rock hind *Epinephelus* sp. (piscivore), moray *Gymnothorax* sp. (piscivore), surgeonfish *Acanthurus* sp. (herbivore), triggerfish *Balistes* sp. (benthophagous) and Gerreidae (detritivores).

During the years 2003 to 2010, among *Karenia* species, only *K. brevis* had been recorded, rarely, in phytoplankton samples from Veracruz waters, It has however caused HABs in the states of Tamaulipas (to the north) and Tabasco (to the

southeast) [2–3, 12–13]. We believe that *Karenia* blooms in Veracruz have been displaced by *Peridinium quinquecorne*, and the northerly winds during the last one or two weeks in December 2009, specifically, the northerlies numbers 19, 20 and 21 [see: <http://smn.cna.gob.mx>], might have favoured higher nutrient concentration as a result of turbulence in this area, which has a permanent load of organic matter derived from a waste treatment plant. Previously, *Karenia sp.* "Mexican hat" has been reported from Florida and Louisiana coasts, blooming several times off the Naples area of the west coast of Florida [9]. The bloom described here, to our knowledge, is the first HAB event of this species in the southern Gulf of Mexico.

Acknowledgements

Financial support (DGI-UV project "Algae of the Veracruzian reef zone, Gulf of Mexico, with emphasis on red algae, diatoms and dinoflagellates" 2007–2009) to YBO is appreciated.

References:

1. Cortés-Altamirano R (ed) 1998. *Las Mareas Rojas*. 161 pp
2. Ramírez-Camarena C *et al* 2002. XII Reunión Nacional de la Sociedad Mexicana de Planctología: 97
3. Ramírez-Camarena C & Hernández-Becerril DU 2006. Memorias del XIII Congreso Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología del Mar (México): 93–94
4. Secretaría de Salud de Veracruz 2007. Programa florecimiento de algas nocivas. 12 pp
5. Cortés-Altamirano R & Sierra-Beltrán AP 2008. *Toxin Reviews* 27: 27–77
6. Campos-Bautista G *et al* 2009. III Taller sobre Florecimientos Algales Nocivos (FAN): Integración del Conocimiento sobre Eventos de FAN en México: 23
7. Barón-Campis S *et al* 2005. *Hidrobiológica* 15: 73–78
8. Aké-Castillo JA 2009. VIII International Meeting of the Mexican Society of Planktology: 64
9. Steidinger KA *et al* 2008. *Nova Hedw Beih* 133: 269–284
10. Steidinger KA 2008. *Harmful Algae* 8: 549–561
11. Maier-Brown *et al* 2006. *Harmful Algae* 5: 199–212
12. Mier y Terán J *et al* 2006. *Salud en Tabasco* 12: 414–422
13. Ramírez-Camarena C *et al* 1999. X Reunión Nacional de la Sociedad Mexicana de Planctología: 17

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ISSHA President's Corner

Route map of activities before the 14th ICHA Conference

Dear HAB experts and managers:

The time for the 14th International Conference on Harmful Algae (Crete, Greece, 1-5 Nov 2010) is approaching, and we are pleased to invite you to participate in important decisions/activities that have now become part of our traditions during the ICHA Conferences. We invite you to become an ISSHA member if you are not still so. Your contributions will help to facilitate the participation of young PhD students and/or experts from developing countries/economies in transition.

The issues for which we need your help are:

1. Nominations for the Yasumoto Award and the Young Scientist Award
2. Travel Awards to attend the 14th International Conference on Harmful Algae
3. Donations for the ISSHA Auction 2010
4. Bids to host the 16th ICHA Conference (2014)

1. Nominations for the Yasumoto Award and the Young Scientist Award

ISSHA members are invited to submit nominations for the Lifetime Achievement Award and the Young Scientist Award. Further information about the awards can be found at

Fig. 1. Rosa Figueroa, Young Scientist 2008 awardee, with her present from ISSHA. A beautifully carved *Gymnodinium catenatum* by Prof. Takayama. Photo by K. Rengefors.

www.isssha.org; click on Awards.

The Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award

This award is offered in recognition of a long and outstanding record of contribution to harmful algal research by an ISSHA member (see the membership list at www.isssha.org). Previous recipients: Dr. F.J.R. (Max) Taylor (2000), Dr. Greta R. Hasle (2002), Dr. Theodore Smayda (2002), Dr. Donald M. Anderson (2006) and Dr. Karen Steidinger (2008).

The Young Scientist Achievement Award

This award is offered in recognition of outstanding achievement in any aspect of harmful algal research by scientists early in their career (i.e. within ten years of receiving their PhD). The award is intended for an exceptional or "break-through" contribution to an area of harmful algae research, rather than a cumulative record of achievement. The nominee should be an ISSHA member (see the membership list at www.isssha.org). Previous recipients: Dr. Chris Scholin (2002), Dr. Rosa I. Figueroa (2008).

Any ISSHA member in good standing may submit nominations for either achievement award, which should include a description of the nominee's contribution (not more than one page). Please, make sure that you and your nominee have renewed membership for the period 2010-2011. Those of you who paid your membership at the beginning of 2008, or at the 13 ICHA Conference in Hong Kong in 2008, paid for the 2008 and 2009 fee.

Nominations should be sent by e-mail to Jennifer Martin (Jennifer.Martin@dfo-mpo.gc.ca), Chair of the Committee on Achievement Awards, to be received before **May 15th 2010**. Please write '**ISSHA Achievement Awards 2010**' in the message subject. Nominations will be considered by the ISSHA Council, and eventual awards will be presented at the XIV HAB Conference in Crete (Greece), 1-5 November 2010.

ISSHA

International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae

Fig. 2. Barrie as auctioneer at the Copenhagen 2006 conference. Photo by M. Lion.

2. Travel Awards to attend the 14th International Conference on Harmful Algae

ISSHA will offer a limited number of travel awards for students and postdoctoral investigators to attend the 14th International Conference on Harmful Algae, 1-5 November 2010, in Hersonissos, Crete, Greece.

Awards are usually limited to a maximum of \$1,000 US.

Successful applicants will need to demonstrate that other sources of funds are available to supplement their award. Among the criteria for selection will be the following:

- Membership in ISSHA (if you are not a member, please join before the applications are reviewed; students get a 50% reduction in their fees)
- Availability of "matching" funds
- First time award applicants will receive priority over those who have received travel support in the past
- Commitment to an oral or a poster presentation
- Quality or unique nature of science to be presented
- Demonstrated financial need

To apply for funds, please send the **application letter (forms will be available on the ISSHA site as of June 1), as a PDF file**, to Clarisse Odebrecht, Chair of Committee on Travel Awards (doclar@furg.br)

following the format that will be available on the ISSHA website in due course. Please write **“ISSHA Travel Awards 2010”** in the message subject. Applications not submitted this way may be rejected.

The deadline for receipt of applications is **July 3, 2010**, with decisions announced approximately one month thereafter.

Additional information about the 14th ICHA can be found at www.hab2010.gr.

3. Donations for the ISSHA Auction 2010

ISSHA auctions during past International Conferences on Harmful Algae have been a tremendous success and are becoming a tradition!! It is an opportunity for the conference participants to bid on donated items. The range of items is broad and may include books, signed reprints, photos, jewellery, T-shirts, paintings, algae-related items, liquor, and scientific equipment. The auction items are donated by ISSHA members from around the world and are used to benefit ISSHA members. Funds collected during the auction are an important income for ISSHA and may represent up to 25% of the total income of the Society. ISSHA was able to offer partial travel support to more than 25 students to attend the Conference in Hong Kong (3-7 Nov 2008).

Barrie Dale has so far been serving as the auctioneer and provocateur, ensuring the evening has been exciting, fun filled and a bit over the top! Please help us make the 14th Conference auction a success.

We need donations for the auction and only your imagination limits what can be donated. Please contact the responsible person for the auction, Anke Kremp (anke.kremp@ymparisto.fi)

Fig. 4. Satisfied ISSHA members with their bargains at the ISSHA auction in Hong Kong 2008. Photo by L. Velo-Suárez.

about your donations for the auction and the way you are going to transport it. **Please, write “ISSHA Auction 2010” in the message subject.** You may also include a picture of your item if you wish. We intend to present a list of items on the ISSHA site (www.issha.org).

We look forward to hearing from you.

4. Request for Bids to Host the 16th International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA)

During 2010, ISSHA members will be asked to vote for which site will host the 16th ICHA (2014) that will follow the 15th ICHA in Korea (2012). The chosen site will be announced during the ISSHA General Assembly held during the 14th ICHA (Crete, November 2010).

Now is the time to ask for bids to host the 16th ICHA, so that voters will have the time to examine the different options and make up their mind. For the first time, ISSHA members in good standing who cannot attend the Conference will have the opportunity to vote by e-mail. **Deadline for e-mail votes will be 15 October 2010.**

Bids should be submitted before **31 July 2010**, and should include the following information:

- Scientists and organizations who will serve as local hosts, including evidence of their prior expertise in the organization and financial management of similar-sized international conferences.
- Description of the meeting venue and capacity of meeting space for a 5-day meeting, including a plenary room, 2 rooms for simultaneous sessions and several small rooms for administrative use and other necessities. Estimated participation is between 400 and 600 people, but sometimes there are surprises, as was the case during the 10th ICHA (St Pete Beach, Florida), with around 800 participants.
- Availability of accommodations at a range of costs, including the number of rooms, distance from the meeting location, and room costs for high and low seasons. If university residence or other inexpensive accommodation is available for students, this will be considered favorably.
- Distance of meeting and lodging facilities from major airport(s) and cost

Fig. 3. Excited ISSHA members inspecting items before the auction in Copenhagen 2006. Photo by M. Lion.

of transportation between airport and meeting and lodging facilities.

- Availability of local public transportation.
 - Expected cost of lunches per day.
 - Availability and distance to restaurants for lunches.
 - Expected level of local support and associated funding, including ability to provide meeting space, audiovisual support, and staff support, at no cost to the international organizers.
 - Dates when the facility would be available in 2014.
 - Plans for mid-week excursions and accompanying persons' activities.
 - HAB scientists who would be responsible for editing the ICHA proceedings¹, including evidence of their prior experience in producing English-language conference proceedings.
- Enquiries and bids should be e-mailed to the President of ISSHA. Bids should be limited to 2-3 pages, plus supplementary illustrations and web links. Information on the previous ICHA venues can be found at the ISSHA website (www.issha.org), by clicking on the “Conferences” navigation button on the left-hand column. Bids will be examined by the ISSHA Council and posted on the ISSHA website.

¹Traditionally, ICHA proceedings have been edited by a group led by the head of the local organizing committee. If the local hosts are not willing to continue this practice, they can ask the ISSHA Committee on Publications and Dissemination to take it over, BUT the money earmarked for the proceedings (in the registration fee) would have to be transferred to ISSHA for the printing and dispatching of the books.

B. Reguera, ISSHA President.
Email: beatriz.reguera@vi.ieo.es

Cont'd from page 5

biotoxins. Prof Yasumoto's talk focused on his more recent research in the field. He discussed alternative methodologies to the mouse bioassay based on protein phosphatase inhibition for OAs, as well as competitive receptor binding assays. He also presented his work on the development of modern chemical alternatives such as MALDI-TOF Mass Spectrometry for the analysis of emergent toxins such as Palytoxin and Ostreocin D. Other invited speakers included Dr. James Lawrence from Health Canada, Ottawa; Dr. Michael Quilliam from the CNRC, Halifax, Canada; Dr. Robert Dickey from FDA, Dauphin Island, GA, USA; Dr. Pedro Burdaspal from AESAN, Madrid, Spain, Dr. Susana Franca from Instituto da Saúde; Dr. Ricardo Jorge, Lisboa, Portugal, and Dr. Aurelia Tubaro from University of Trieste, Italy. Among the invited speakers, Drs. Lawrence, Quilliam, Dickey, and Burdaspal focused their discussions primarily on the importance of developing and improving analytical methodologies as alternatives to animal assays, the need for validated methods for existing and emergent

toxins, and the critical need for the development of certified reference materials to achieve these goals. The toxicology of the marine toxins and their impact on public health were also discussed by Dr. Tubaro and Dr. Franca. The seminar ended with a round table, with the invited speakers responding to questions from the audience. The majority of these discussions related to the applicability of modern analytical techniques versus the mouse bioassay, the advantages and disadvantages of

these modern techniques, and concluded with the speakers restating the need for fully validated alternative methods able to efficiently and reliably determine marine biotoxins.

Congratulations to Professor Yasumoto on behalf of the Marine Biotoxins Community!

A. Gago-Martínez, University of Vigo, Vigo, Spain.

Email: anagago@uvigo.es

Photos by M. Lion

AUGUST 2010

8th International Conference on Toxic Cyanobacteria (ICTC8)

Istanbul, Turkey, 29th of August – 4th of September 2010

ICTC8 will take place in Istanbul hosted by the Istanbul University, Faculty of Fisheries, Department of Inland Waters and Association of Aquaculture Engineering.

The Conference will once again bring together researchers from all over the world for five days of intensive scientific meeting with the aim to examine the whole of Toxic Cyanobacteria, that extends our knowledge, improves on our practice, and widens our friendship networks.

Important dates:

- Deadline for Abstracts Submission: May 15, 2010
- Information for Accepted Abstracts: June 30, 2010
- Deadline for Early Registration: May 31, 2010

More info at: www.cyano2010.org

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